

EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE TEMPERATURE ON STRUCTURAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF Sb_xS_y THIN FILMS GROWN BY CMBD METHOD

T.M.Razikov –

D.Sc., Prof., head of Lab.;

K.M.Kuchkarov –

D.Sc., Senior Researcher PTI;

D.Z.Isakov, M.P.Pirimmetov

master PhD student PTI,

R.R.Khurramov

master Senior Researcher PTI,

Q.F. Shakhriev

bachelor student NUU. Uzbekistan.

1. Introduction. Currently, a lot of research has been done on the thin film of Sb_2S_3 , which is used as an absorbing in various studies. One of the main reasons for this is its competitive physical properties [1-3]. Today, SbS-based thin films are grown and researched in several methods (VTE, CSS, CBD and etc.) [4-6]. The primary goal of the ongoing research is to optimize the physical properties of Sb_2S_3 thin films and obtain a solar cell with high efficiency based on them. Therefore, the quality of the obtained films depends on their structural, morphological and optical properties. In this work, for the first time, we managed to grow Sb_xS_y thin films using the CMBD method. We studied its structural and morphological characteristics and the laws of dependence on the substrate temperature.

2. Experiments. The experiment started with cutting soda lime glasses in certain sizes ($14 \times 14 \text{ mm}^2$). Subsequently, they were chemically cleaned with a soapy solution, and the pads in an ultrasonic bath were washed in solutions of acetic acid, distilled water, and ethanol. Then the substrate glasses were dried in nitrogen (N) gas. Cleaned glass slides were placed in a chemical molecular beam deposition (CMBD) device [7]. The process was carried out inside a cylindrical quartz chamber. The distance between the base and the source is $d=10 \text{ cm}$. A molybdenum wire was used to heat the source. The substrates were heated by an external heater. The temperature of the substrate and the source was determined using a thermocouple made of chrome-aluminum wire. A high-quality Sb_2S_3 compound (purity 99.999%; Chemsavers) was

used as a source. substrate temperatures of 300°C, 350°C, 400°C, and 450°C were selected for the experiment.

3. Results and discussion. Figure 1 shows XRD images of Sb_2S_3 thin films grown at various substrate temperatures. At all substrate temperatures (except 450°C), the XRD analysis revealed distinct peaks corresponding to (020), (120), (130), (211), (221), (301), and (240) planes of Sb_2S_3 , indicating its orthorhombic structure as per JCPDS pdf 00-006-0474.

Fig 1. XRD patterns of Sb_xS_y thin films at different substrate temperatures

Fig 2. Raman spectra of Sb_xS_y thin films at different substrate temperatures

Additionally, peaks corresponding to Sb were observed at (012), (104), and (110) planes in the Sb_2S_3 thin films, consistent with JCPDS pdf 01-085-1322, across all substrate temperatures. Notably, at the highest substrate temperature of 450°C, the intensity of Sb_2S_3 peaks notably diminished, particularly (020), (120), (130), (211), (221), and (501), while peaks corresponding to Sb, such as (110) and (202), increased. This observation suggests that excessively high substrate temperatures are unfavorable for Sb_2S_3 thin film formation. The consistent presence of Sb peaks in all samples indicates a high proportion of Sb within the Sb_2S_3 thin film composition. For Sb_xS_y thin films, phase analysis was carried out in order to check the bonding of Sb with S. (Fig. 2). Raman spectroscopy analysis showed that intensity peaks at 110 cm^{-1} , 150 cm^{-1} , 237 cm^{-1} , 280 cm^{-1} and 310 cm^{-1} are present in all Sb_2S_3 thin films. This confirms that the main lattice structure is preserved in the grown samples. It can be seen from the figure that the intensity of the 280 cm^{-1} and 310 cm^{-1} peaks increases with the increase of the base temperature. These peak values correspond to Sb-S vibration phases [8]. The intense peak at 237 cm^{-1} is almost unchanged with the change of the

base temperature. The band at 237 cm^{-1} corresponds to symmetric S-Sb-S bending modes [9,10]. Intense peaks at 110 cm^{-1} and 150 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of Sb-Sb phases in thin films [11]. In addition, there are several intense peaks at 80, 189, 372, 252, and 450 cm^{-1} in SbS thin films, and these peaks correspond to Sb_2O_3 phases [12]. It can be seen that peaks at 80, 252, 372 and 450 cm^{-1} , which were not observed in the films, appeared at the substrate temperature of 350°C . The intense peak of 72 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the Sb_2O_4 phase, decreased with increasing substrate temperature [13].

Morphological properties of Sb_xS_y thin films grown by CMBD method were studied using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM). SEM micrographs show that Sb_xS_y thin films prepared at substrate temperatures of 300°C and 350°C have a much smoother surface (Fig. 3). Sb_xS_y films consist of nanosheets with a length of 1-2 μm and a thickness of 100-500 nm. Some of the grains coalesced to form 2-3 μm large grains. Such associations were also observed in samples obtained by the VTD method [14]. At the substrate temperature of 300°C , the grains were smaller and the spaces between the grains were larger. An increase in the temperature of the substrate led to an increase in the size of the grains and a decrease in the spaces between them. At the substrate temperature of 450°C , the grains reached the largest size (2.5 μm). Also, the gaps between them have grown significantly. Figure 4 shows the AFM images of the samples. The measured surface roughness parameters are listed in Table 1. The RMS surface roughness S_q values were found to be between 0.3206 and 0.96675 nm. As the temperature of the substrate increases, the roughness increases.

300°C **350°C** **400°C** **450°C**
Fig. 3. Surface morphology of Sb_xS_y thin films at different substrate temperatures

Fig. 4. 2D topography obtained on an AFM of the surface of Sb_xS_y thin films at different substrate temperatures

Table 1. Surface roughness parameters of Sb_xS_y thin films at different substrate temperatures

$T_{sub}, ^\circ C$	300	350	400	450
Average roughness $S_a, \mu m$	0,2526	0,3204	0,727	0,76775
RMS roughness $S_q, \mu m$	0,3206	0,417	0,9062	0,96675
Ssk asymmetry Ssk	0,8554	0,9118	0,7362	0,5165
Ska kurtosis Ska	4,3714	4,8162	3,2544	3,1985

4. Conclusion. The study investigated the effect of substrate temperature on the structural and morphological properties of Sb_xS_y thin films grown by the CMBD method. The XRD analysis revealed an orthorhombic crystal structure for the films grown at different substrate temperatures, with notable changes in peak intensities as the temperature varied. Raman spectroscopy confirmed the preservation of the main lattice structure across all samples, with variations in peak intensities attributed to Sb-S vibration phases and symmetric S-Sb-S bending modes. SEM and AFM analysis provided insights into the morphological properties, revealing changes in grain size and surface roughness with increasing substrate temperature. Overall, these findings contribute to our understanding of the growth parameters influencing the properties of Sb_xS_y thin films and provide valuable insights for optimizing their performance in various applications.

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